

Sentence Fragments and their Place in the Sentence in German and Uzbek

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Abstract: This article describes the importance of grammatical knowledge in the perfect mastery of foreign languages, the role of sentences in German languages, the change of sentence fragments according to the purpose of the sentence, as well as the location of sentence fragments in Uzbek languages, their peculiarities, differences in the place of sentences in German and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: sentence fragments, have, cross-sectionality, predicativity, modality, tense category, person-number, category concept, communicative, nominative, morphological.

Introduction.

In teaching a foreign language, it is important to analyze its practical aspects, specifically its grammatical features. Studying the characteristics of practical grammar in foreign languages, particularly in the German language, and exploring methods to utilize these features during communication processes is one of the pressing issues in foreign language teaching methodology. Among such important topics, we can also include the subject: "Sentence parts in the German language, their distinctive features of usage, and the sentence parts in the Uzbek language along with their unique aspects."

Analysis of Literature and Methods.

In studying the topic "Sentence parts in German and Uzbek languages and their distinctive features in sentence structure," we used the method of analyzing scientific literature and exploring the opinions of scholars on the subject. The ideas of scholars such as V. Jung, Helbig Buscha, M.G. Arseneva, O. Moskalskaya, and V. Schmidt were referenced. We also utilized literature studied by scholars in our country, including S. Saidov, G'. Zikrillayev, M. Mirzayev, I. Rasulov, J. Buronov, Ph.D. Associate Professor M. Sattorov, Ph.D. Associate Professor R. Safoyeva, and Ph.D. Associate Professor L. Kholiyorov.

Methods Used.

One of the methods we employed in studying the topic was the comparative method. Through this method, we learned that the placement of sentence parts in both German and Uzbek languages is relatively fixed, adhering to certain patterns. However, we also observed that in some cases, for stylistic purposes, the placement of sentence parts may change, leading to deviations from the established rules.

Results and Discussions.

Language, as a means of communication among members of society, is realized through sentences. A sentence is the main tool for forming, expressing, and conveying thoughts, and generally for exchanging ideas. (1.24) The issue of defining a sentence has not yet been fully resolved. Through this topic, we examined the unique aspects of sentence part positioning in the German and Uzbek languages, and their differences were outlined.

Concept of Sentence and Sentence Parts.

1. A sentence is primarily formed by the combination of words, and this combination follows grammatical rules.
2. One of the important features of a sentence is predicativity. In a sentence, the speaker's attitude towards the expressed thought is conveyed. This is called predicativity. (2.65) Predicativity includes categories such as modality, tense, and person-number.

A sentence and its parts are the manifestation of our thoughts in tangible form through language. The system of sentences ensures communication and exchange of ideas between people. This feature of a sentence, as opposed to a word or phrase, is demonstrated in the following way:

| Word Combination | Sentence |

| Delegation visit | Die Delegation ist angekommen |

| Name of the event | Event reported |

A sentence can also perform a naming function.

In conclusion, a sentence is a small, relatively independent linguistic unit that performs cognitive, communicative, and nominative functions. It is a unit constructed according to the laws of each language.

Unique Features of Sentence Parts in German and Uzbek.

When discussing the placement of sentence parts, we found it appropriate to rely on Helbig Buscha's ideas. In German, the position of sentence parts is determined by various factors, including:

1. Syntactic conditions.
2. Morphological conditions.
3. Purpose-related conditions.

1. Syntactic Conditions are related to the predicate. Some sentence parts have fixed positions, while others do not.

Example:

1. Er liest heute ein interessantes Buch. (First position)
2. Liest er heute ein interessantes Buch? (Second position)
3. ...dass er heute ein interessantes Buch liest. (Final position)

As we can see, the verb lesen ("to read") changes position in three different structures. Similarly, we observe the change in sentence part order in declarative, interrogative, imperative, and compound sentences. In contrast, this does not occur in Uzbek:

1. Men bugun qiziq kitob o'qidim.
2. Bugun men qiziq kitob o'qidim.

3. Men bugun qiziq kitob o'qidimmi?
4. Men dugonamga bugun qiziq kitob o'qiganimni aytdim.

In German, the verb position is variable, while in Uzbek, it remains unchanged.

2. Morphological Conditions relate to parts of speech other than the predicate and manifest as follows:

Example: The use of articles with sentence parts.

Ich schenke dem Kind ein Buch.

Ich schenke das Buch einem Kind.

In this case, we observe the change in articles used with nouns in the sentence. However, in Uzbek, where the concepts of gender and articles are absent, this phenomenon is not observed:

Men bolaga kitob sovg'a qildim.

3. In German, the sentence parts change according to the purpose of the sentence. This can be observed in the following examples:

In German, the position of sentence parts may vary depending on the topic, information structure, and communicative purpose.

Subject in the main position. The typical order of words is subject-predicate-secondary parts of the sentence.

Example: Das Kind spielt im Hof. (Subject + Predicate + Adverbial)

Topic in the main position. (Secondary part + Predicate + Subject)

Example: Im Hof spielt das Kind. (Adverbial + Predicate + Subject)

Contrastive emphasis.

Im Hof spielt nur das Kind. (The word "nur" emphasizes that the child is alone.)

In German, we can provide many examples of such cases. From this, we see that the position of sentence parts in German is variable.

In contrast, in Uzbek, the position of sentence parts is relatively flexible, with the typical structure being subject + secondary parts + predicate. This means that in most cases, the predicate occupies the last position in a sentence.

In declarative sentences: (Subject + Secondary parts + Predicate)

Example: Bola hovlida o'ynayapti. (The child is playing in the yard.)

In interrogative sentences: The word order in interrogative sentences is generally the same as in declarative sentences, with the only difference being the presence of an interrogative word.

Example: Bola qayerda o'ynayapti? (Where is the child playing?)

In imperative sentences: In most cases, the predicate takes the first position and is often the only word in the sentence.

Example: O'yna! (Play!), O'qi! (Read!), Bor! (Go!)

Conclusion.

Based on the topic discussed, we can say that each language has its own grammatical rules. For example, since German and Uzbek belong to different language groups, there are many

differences between them, including in the arrangement of sentence parts. From the examples above, we can conclude that there are often differences in the word order of sentences in German and Uzbek.

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